

Social Science Data Archives – 20 years of experience in digital preservation of research data

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Social Science Data Archives (ADP)

<http://www.fdv.uni-lj.si/>

- 1997
- Slovenian national data repository for social sciences
 - 600 social science surveys with data in a data catalogue + 150 with metadata
 - cca. 1200 users registered in 2017 (90 % education, 10 % scientific/research purpose)
 - 168 survey data used for detailed secondary-analysis in 2017
- Member of [CESSDA ERIC](#)
- Trusted Data repository certification
- Involved in EU [projects](#)

 ADP Social Science Data Archives
<http://www.adp.fdv.uni-lj.si/eng/>
CTS Certification 2017-2019

Two Views of Data Archives

Physical Assets and Intangible Assets.

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ADP User Satisfaction Survey 2016

Purpose of use (multiple responses) (n=521)

Source: [CESSDA SaW Case Study User Satisfaction Surveys](#)

Evaluation of ADP services

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Data Publication

It is expected that a Data Publication will ensure that data will potentially be considered as a first-class research output | Knowledge Exchange (2013).

Publishing with a capital "P"

- Properly documented with metadata;
- Reviewed for quality;
- Searchable and discoverable in catalogues (or databases);
- Citable in articles

Publishing with a small "p"

- there are no guarantees that the data will be there after some time or that the files will not get corrupted.

Data Publishing Routes

- + Journal supplementary material service
- + Institutional data repository
- + General purpose repository
- + Domain specific data repository
- + Trusted domain specific data repository

Why publish with CESSDA archives?

- (Trusted) domain specific data repositories
- Advantage of having expert help within reach
- Accessible and protected when needed
- Comprehensibility
- Findability and visibility
- Accessibility and reusability
- Longivity
- Quality

Scientific credit

CESSDA Training Working Group (2017). CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide. Bergen, Norway: CESSDA ERIC. Retrieved from <https://www.cessda.eu/DMGuide>

ADP evaluates the importance of research data for science and their long-term usability.

Acquired data are acknowledged as a scientific publication in their own right and represent a basis for quantitative assessments of scientific excellence in accordance with the **criteria of the Slovenian Research Agency.**

Open data and RDM activities on national level

ADP being involved in:

[„OPEN DATA“ Action plan](#) for establishing a system of open access to research data funded by public sources (project funded by Slovenian Ministry of Education, Science and Sport)

In 2011, 22 interviews, 17 different disciplines

REPUBLIC OF SLOVENIA
GOVERNMENT OF THE REPUBLIC OF SLOVENIA

[National strategy of open access to scientific publications and research data in Slovenia 2015-2020](#) (2015)

[Action Plan of the National Strategy of Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in Slovenia 2015-2020](#) (2017)

Related legislation:

- ✓ [General Data Protection Regulation](#) (2018)
- ✓ [Research and Development Activity Act](#)

Thank you!!!

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